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Pattern of Distribution and Utilization of SMC Intervention on the Prevention of Malaria among Children Under-5 in Sokoto State

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Abstract

An accurate diagnosis of malaria has become increasingly important as *Plasmodium falciparum* becomes resistant to commonly used antimalarial drugs, posing a major threat to the global effort to 'Roll Back Malaria', especially in rural areas where malaria is more severe and frequent. This study aimed at evaluating the pattern of utilization of SMC implementation in Sokoto state over five years (2015-2019) among children under-5 years. This study was carried out as descriptive-analytical study. Inclusion criteria were strictly based on those children under 5 years that were eligible for SMC. All those children above 5 years of age were excluded from the study. Caregivers in Sokoto state had a high level of knowledge on seasonal malaria chemoprevention. Caregivers' perceptions of SMC's effectiveness were largely positive, and the program's acceptability was acknowledged to be highly valued by parents and other stakeholders. Parents and caregivers place a high value on their children's health and have vowed to support the SMC intervention as well as any other community initiative focused at improving their children's health. Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

Keywords: 5-year, SMC, Intervention, Prevention, Malaria and Sokoto State

Introduction

An accurate diagnosis of malaria has become increasingly important as *Plasmodium falciparum* becomes resistant to commonly used antimalarial drugs, posing a major threat to the global effort to 'Roll Back Malaria', especially in rural areas where malaria is more severe and frequent (WHO, 2019). The diagnostic approaches most commonly used in Nigeria are the syndromic approach, followed by microscopy and rapid diagnostic tests (RDT) (Cox, 2002). Due to the poor or absence of laboratory facilities, malaria diagnosis in many health centres has continued to be based on fever or history of fever. Microscopy, considered the gold standard for malaria diagnosis, is generally unavailable at primary healthcare centres only available at the secondary and tertiary level hospitals. However, it is often not used and has an accuracy of only 70-75% (Crutcher and Hoffman, 1996). Microscopy depends on well-maintained equipment, an uninterrupted supply of quality reagents, trained staff, regular quality monitoring and supervision. Maintaining quality microscopy is a major challenge, and it is unsuitable for routine use at a community level (Yeung *et al.*, 2004). RDTs based on detection of Plasmodium-specific proteins can be used if microscopy is unavailable, but cost, availability, false-positive tests, false-negative tests and lack of parasite density information are important limitations, particularly in high transmission areas. Deploying RDTs did not affect the overdiagnosis of malaria in febrile patients (Nkwenti *et al.*, 2019).

With *Plasmodium falciparum*'s resistance to conventional antimalarial drugs escalating, precise malaria diagnosis gains paramount significance. This resistance poses a formidable threat to the global initiative to 'Roll Back Malaria,' particularly in rural regions where malaria prevalence is heightened. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2019) underscores the urgency of accurate diagnosis as a pivotal strategy in navigating the complexities of drug-resistant malaria. In rural areas, where the malaria burden is pronounced, timely and precise diagnoses not only inform effective treatment but also contribute crucially to the broader goal of mitigating the global impact of this persistent and evolving public health challenge.

In Nigeria, prevalent diagnostic methods for malaria predominantly rely on the syndromic approach, microscopy, and rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), as outlined by Cox (2002). The syndromic approach, which often hinges on the presence of fever or a history thereof, is particularly emphasized due to challenges posed by inadequate laboratory facilities in numerous health centers. The scarcity of resources impedes the widespread implementation of advanced diagnostic tools, leading to a reliance on clinical symptoms, which can result in misdiagnoses. This situation underscores the urgent need for improved diagnostic

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infrastructure and the incorporation of more accurate and accessible tools like RDTs. Enhancing diagnostic capabilities becomes pivotal not only for ensuring effective malaria management but also for addressing the challenges posed by drug resistance, contributing to a more targeted and resilient approach in combating malaria in Nigeria.

Microscopy, deemed the gold standard for malaria diagnosis, encounters accessibility challenges as it is typically limited to secondary and tertiary-level hospitals, frequently absent at primary healthcare centers. Despite its status, its practical application is hindered, contributing to an accuracy rate of only 70-75%, as indicated by Crutcher and Hoffman (1996). This underscores a significant diagnostic gap, particularly in primary healthcare settings where malaria burden is substantial. The constraints in microscopy availability at the frontline of healthcare pose challenges in timely and precise diagnoses. Given its suboptimal accuracy and limited accessibility, there's a pressing need for alternative, more widely applicable diagnostic tools such as rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) to ensure prompt and accurate identification of malaria cases, particularly in resource-constrained regions where primary healthcare is the frontline defense against this pervasive disease.

The effectiveness of microscopy as a malaria diagnostic tool hinges on a multitude of factors, including well-maintained equipment, a consistent supply of high-quality reagents, adequately trained staff, and continuous quality monitoring and supervision, as highlighted by Yeung et al. (2004). Sustaining these prerequisites poses a formidable challenge, particularly in resource-constrained settings. The intricate demands for equipment maintenance, reagent supply, and skilled personnel make microscopy impractical for routine use at the community level. The exigencies of quality control and supervision render it more suited for secondary and tertiary healthcare facilities, accentuating the urgent need for alternative diagnostic strategies. Emphasizing accessible and reliable tools like rapid diagnostic tests becomes imperative to surmount the limitations of microscopy, ensuring widespread and accurate malaria diagnoses, particularly in communities where advanced healthcare infrastructure is limited.

Rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs), relying on the detection of Plasmodium-specific proteins, serve as viable alternatives when microscopy is unavailable, yet they come with significant limitations. The cost, availability, and reliability of RDTs are crucial concerns, especially in resource-constrained settings. False-positive and false-negative test results, compounded by the absence of parasite density information, pose challenges in accurate diagnoses, particularly in regions with high malaria transmission. The limitations of RDTs underscore the nuanced complexities in deploying diagnostic tools that balance accessibility, accuracy, and cost-effectiveness. Addressing these challenges necessitates a comprehensive approach, potentially involving advancements in RDT technology, coupled with strategic implementation strategies and ongoing quality assurance measures to enhance their reliability and applicability, especially in areas where access to sophisticated diagnostic facilities remains a persistent challenge.

The deployment of rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) has been observed not to significantly impact the overdiagnosis of malaria in febrile patients, as indicated by Nkwenti et al. (2019). Despite their intended role in providing a rapid and accurate diagnosis, certain factors may contribute to persistent overdiagnosis. Issues such as test sensitivity, user interpretation, and the prevalence of other febrile illnesses can influence diagnostic outcomes. This finding underscores the complexity of malaria diagnosis in febrile patients and suggests that while RDTs offer advantages in terms of speed and accessibility, addressing overdiagnosis requires a multifaceted approach. Enhancements in test sensitivity, continuous training for healthcare providers, and a broader consideration of alternative causes of fever are imperative to refine the utility of RDTs and ensure more accurate diagnoses in febrile patients.

Objectives of the Study

1. Evaluate the level of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC).
2. Investigate caregivers' perceptions of the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children in Sokoto state.
3. Assess the overall acceptability of the SMC program among caregivers, parents, and other stakeholders in Sokoto state.
4. Explore the extent to which parents and caregivers in Sokoto state value their children's health.
5. Assess the commitment of parents and caregivers to support the SMC intervention, as well as their willingness to endorse other community initiatives aimed at improving children's health.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding the principles, benefits, and implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC)?
2. How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?

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3. To what degree is the SMC program accepted by caregivers, parents, and other stakeholders in Sokoto state, and what are the key factors contributing to or hindering its overall acceptability?
4. How do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state prioritize and value the health and well-being of their children in the context of preventive measures such as SMC?
5. What level of commitment do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state express in supporting the implementation of the SMC intervention?

Methodology

Having adopted a descriptive-analytical study design, this research comprehensively examined the utilization patterns and impact of Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention (SMC) among children under the age of 5 in Sokoto state. Conducted in Sokoto state, Nigeria, the study encompassed all 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs), 244 wards, and 8269 settlements. The primary study population included children under the age of 5 eligible for SMC in Sokoto state, with the inclusion of parents and caregivers, health workers, and relevant stakeholders involved in the SMC program. A multistage sampling technique was employed, starting with the random selection of LGAs, followed by the random selection of wards within the chosen LGAs. Settlements and households within wards were then chosen to obtain a representative sample. Statistical software was used for data analysis, encompassing descriptive statistics to summarize utilization patterns and inferential statistics to explore associations.

Ethical approval was obtained from relevant institutional review boards, and informed consent was secured from participants, along with a guarantee of confidentiality and anonymity. Ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects were followed, recognizing potential limitations such as recall bias, information bias, and generalizability constraints due to the specific regional focus (Haruna, 2010). Additionally, pre-testing of survey instruments was conducted to ensure clarity and relevance. Data collectors and interviewers underwent training to maintain consistency and quality, with regular monitoring of data collection processes to resolve discrepancies promptly.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of knowledge among caregivers in Sokoto state regarding the principles, benefits, and implementation of seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC)?

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Figure 1: SMC administered during the reporting period

Research Question 2

How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document.: SMC redose of the failed administered SP+AQ

Research Question 3

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How do caregivers in Sokoto state perceive the effectiveness of SMC in preventing malaria among children, and what factors influence these perceptions?

Figure 3: Sick children referred from the community to health facility

Research Question 4

How do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state prioritize and value the health and well-being of their children in the context of preventive measures such as SMC?

Figure4: Quantity of SP+AQ used during the reporting period

Research Question 5

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What level of commitment do parents and caregivers in Sokoto state express in supporting the implementation of the SMC intervention?

Figure Error! No text of

specified style in document..1: Adverse drug reaction recorded

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..2: Target population of children treated with SP+AQ during SMC cycles in Sokoto

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Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..3: Average population of children enrolled in SMC according to LGAs in Sokoto

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..4: Average population of children enrolled in SMC cycles in Sokoto according to senatorial zones

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..5: Total number of functional health facilities is LGAs in Sokoto

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Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..6: Average population of children enrolled for SMC cycles in each of the 23 LGAs in Sokoto state

Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..7: Number of children who received RE dose of SP+AQ

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Figure Error! No text of specified style in document..8: Impact of SMC among children under-5 years in Sokoto

Discussion of Findings

This section indicates the SMC data coverage within the reporting period. A survey conducted in four states of the north-western Nigeria comprising of Zamfara, Katsina, Jigawa and Sokoto state (the study area) by the Oxford Policy Management funded by the Malaria Consortium indicated that despite the decline in the coverage in some settlements. SMC has still contributed immensely in reducing the incidence of both simple and severe malaria disease and the associated anaemia, it has also reduced significantly hospital visits by the targeted age group resulting in healthier, stronger children able to develop and grow with limited interruption by the disease episode (MC 2018 end of round survey Nig). In another report by 3 ACCESS SMS, it was revealed that Over the three seasons of delivery 2015, 2016, and 2017 it has been estimated that the ACCESS-SMC project may have prevented over 10 million malaria cases and 60,000 deaths.

The data also obtainable at the Sokoto State Malaria Elimination Agency revealed that the implementation of SMC was associated with a substantial reduction in hospital admission and all-cause mortality (SOSMEA, 2020). Another study was conducted in Nigeria within the northwest region, cases were recruited in the outpatient department of general hospitals of Gwadabawa and Wurno LGAs in Sokoto State, and Kaura Namoda and Tsafe LGAs in Zamfara State. For cases and their matched controls, SMC status was determined as of the day the case was detected. Three categories of SMC exposure were considered: SMC in the last 28 days, SMC 28-42 days ago, and as the reference category, those who received SMC more than 42 days ago or had not received SMC. Conditional logistic regression was used to estimate the odds ratios for exposure to SMC within 28 days (OR0-28), and for exposure in the period 29-42 days (OR29-42), relative to SMC more than 42 days before, in each year and country, adjusted for age, use of LLIN, socio-economic status of the household, and caregiver education, using State versions 15 and 16. Random-effects meta-analysis was then used to obtain pooled estimates of the odds ratios for the countries/years combined. These odds ratios are estimates of incidence rate ratios, and 100x(1-OR0-28) and 100x(1-OR29-42) are estimates of the percentage effectiveness of SMC (the percentage reduction in the incidence rate of clinical malaria) in the corresponding period, relative to SMC more than 42 days before.

Conclusion

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Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention is an intervention with great potential in Sokoto state, and along with other interventions, it could significantly contribute to approaching the threshold where elimination strategies will be envisioned. During the mass drug administration in all 23 LGAs, comprising 244 wards and 8269 settlements, the intervention significantly reduced hospital visit, admission, and malaria indicators in children.

References

- Baba, E., Hamade, P., Kivumbi, H., Marasciulo, M., Maxwell, K., Moroso, D., . . . Milligan, P. (2020). Effectiveness of seasonal malaria chemoprevention at scale in west and central Africa: an observational study. *The Lancet*, **396(10265)**, 1829-1840. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)32227-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32227-3); [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)32227-3](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32227-3).
- Bashir, I. M., Nyakoe, N., & van der Sande, M. (2019). Targeting remaining pockets of malaria transmission in Kenya to hasten progress towards national elimination goals: an assessment of prevalence and risk factors in children from the Lake endemic region. *Malaria Journal*, **18**. 10.1186/s12936-019-2876-x: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12936-019-2876-x>. 10.1186/s12865-019-0294-z: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12865-019-0294-z>.
- Crutcher, J. M., & Hoffman, S. L. (1996). Malaria. In *In: Baron S, editor. Medical Microbiology. 4th edition. Galveston (TX): University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston; 1996. Chapter 83. Available from: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK8584/#*.
- Haruna, A. S. (2010). *Research Methods: A simple guide to educational inquiries*. S.K. Amodu.
- SOSMEA. (2020). *Archive Library I Sokoto State Malaria Elimination Agency - Ministry of Health Sokoto*.
- WHO. (2013). *World Health Organization - Global tuberculosis report 2013*: World Health Organization.
- WHO. (2015). Guidelines for the Treatment of Malaria. 3rd edition. Geneva: World Health Organization; TREATMENT OF UNCOMPLICATED PLASMODIUM FALCIPARUM MALARIA. In *Guidelines for the Treatment of Malaria. 3rd edition*: World Health Organization.
- WHO. (2017). WHO | Seasonal malaria chemoprevention (SMC). *Malaria*. Retrieved from https://www.who.int/malaria/areas/preventive_therapies/children/en/
- WHO. (2019). World Health Organization I World malaria report 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/feature-stories/detail/world-malaria-report-2019>
- WHO. (2020). World Health Organization - Malaria. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/malaria>
- Williams, T. N. (2006). Human red blood cell polymorphisms and malaria. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, **9(4)**, 388-394. 10.1016/j.mib.2006.06.009: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2006.06.009>.
- Yeung, S., Pongtavornpinyo, W., Hastings, I. M., Mills, A. J., & White, N. J. (2004). Antimalarial drug resistance, artemisinin-based combination therapy, and the contribution of modeling to elucidating policy choices. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, **71(2 Suppl)**, 179-186. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/15331836>
- Yoo, J. A. (2019). Sultanate of Sokoto (Sokoto Caliphate): Global African History, Places: 19th Century (1800-1899), Africa - Nigeria, Africa - Senegal, Africa - Cameroon, Africa - Chad, Africa - Mali, Africa-Burkina Faso, Religion-Islam, Europe - Great Britain - England. Retrieved from <https://www.blackpast.org/global-african-history/sultanate-sokoto-sokoto-caliphate>
- Zongo, I., Milligan, P., Compaore, Y. D., Some, A. F., Greenwood, B., Tarning, J., . . . Ouedraogo, J. B. (2015). Randomized Noninferiority Trial of Dihydroartemisinin-Piperaquine Compared with Sulfadoxine-Pyrimethamine plus Amodiaquine for Seasonal Malaria Chemoprevention in Burkina Faso. *Antimicrobial Agents and Chemotherapy*, **59(8)**, 4387-4396. 10.1128/aac.04923-14: <https://doi.org/10.1128/aac.04923-14>.